

Second International HPC workshop

Deliverable D1.5

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Lead authors:

Fondazione Centro Euro-Mediterraneo sui Cambiamenti Climatici (CMCC), Giovanni Aloisio, Silvia Mocavero, Antonio Aloisio, Sandro Fiore

Other contributing authors:

Deutsches Klimarechenzentrum GmbH (DKRZ), Joachim Biercamp, Philipp Neumann, Chiara Bearzotti
European Centre for Medium-Range Weather Forecasts (ECMWF), Peter Bauer

Contacts: esiwace@dkrz.de

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1. Abstract /publishable summary

This deliverable is a report on the 5th ENES HPC workshop, which was held in Lecce (IT) on 17-18 May 2018. The main focus of the workshop, building on the previous ENES HPC workshops (Lecce, 2011; Toulouse, 2013; Hamburg, 2014 and Toulouse, 2016) was on high-resolution modelling. It also addressed other issues such as Domain Specific Languages, coupling & I/O tools and involved discussions about European and international HPC ecosystems and data centres support, as well as the relationship with the EC strategy on HPC. The deliverable includes the list of experts of the Programme Committee, the workshop agenda and the list of attendees, as well as the main outcomes of the meeting and a brief report on the conclusions.

2. Conclusion & Results

As the previous workshops of the same series, the 5th ENES HPC workshop was an opportunity to put together scientists working on the HPC challenges in the Weather and Climate context. For the first time, the focus of the meeting was on the use of HPC (in the pre-exascale era) to run very high-resolution simulations (the ESIWACE target is 1-km). The participation was heterogeneous both at a geographical and background level. European and international speakers were invited and representatives from Climate & Weather and HPC communities as well as from data centres and the industry attended the meeting. A fruitful exchange has been achieved between the users community, which provides the requirements, and the HPC community that promotes innovative and efficient solutions to the open issues. The efforts to develop European and international high-resolution models and the main scientific results, as well as the achieved computational performance, have been presented. Comparable results in terms of SYPD (0.1-0.5), resolution (5km) and scalability (5K cores) of the models have been shown and some open questions discussed.

3. Project objectives

This deliverable contributes directly and indirectly to the achievement of many macro-objectives and specific goals indicated in section 1.1 of the Description of the Action:

Macro-objectives	Contribution of this deliverable?
Improve the efficiency and productivity of numerical weather and climate simulation on high-performance computing platforms	Yes
Support the end-to-end workflow of global Earth system modelling for weather and climate simulation in high performance computing environments	Yes
The European weather and climate science community will drive the governance structure that defines the services to be provided by ESIWACE	Yes
Foster the interaction between industry and the weather and climate community on the exploitation of high-end computing systems, application codes and services.	Yes
Increase competitiveness and growth of the European HPC industry	Yes

Specific goals in the workplan	Contribution of this deliverable?
Provide services to the user community that will impact beyond the lifetime of the project.	No
Improve scalability and shorten the time-to-solution for climate and operational weather forecasts at increased resolution and complexity to be run on	Yes

future extreme-scale HPC systems.	
Foster usability of the available tools, software, computing and data handling infrastructures.	Yes
Pursue exploitability of climate and weather model results.	No
Establish governance of common software management to avoid unnecessary and redundant development and to deliver the best available solutions to the user community.	No
Provide open access to research results and open source software at international level.	Yes
Exploit synergies with other relevant activities and projects and also with the global weather and climate community	Yes

4. Detailed report on the deliverable

This section reports about the work done to organise the 5th ENES HPC workshop. This is the last workshop after the previous ones held in Lecce (2011), Toulouse (2013), Hamburg (2014) and Toulouse (2016). The **main goal** of the HPC workshops series is to put together the climate and HPC communities and, since 2015 when the ESIWACE project started, the weather community. The ENES HPC Task Force has a key role in the definition of the topics to be addressed during the meetings.

In details:

- the 1st workshop, held in Lecce (December 15-16, 2011) and organised in the project IS-ENES context, was dedicated to sharing the experience in developing new dycores and aimed to highlight the main issues, both at methodological and computational level. The main outcome was the need to establish collaboration projects where generic issues like coupling and comparison/evaluation of different models would be addressed
- these aspects have been exploited during the 2nd workshop, held in Toulouse (beginning of 2013, funded by IS-ENES) when the main developments on dycores were introduced as well as an overview of the related European initiatives, collaboration projects, European and International ESMs and closely related high-performance computing issues. The need to establish an interdisciplinary team, putting together the expertise of climate scientists, mathematicians and computational scientists, emerged in order to re-think numerical models and improve the algorithms parallelism level to take advantage of peta-exascale computing
- the co-design spirit was extended to technology providers during the 3rd workshop, held in Hamburg (March 2014, funded by IS-ENES2), where, for the first time, vendors were invited to provide relevant info on the hardware trend and its impact on climate models. Another important aspect of the third workshop was related to the models intercomparison through the definition of a set of metrics for the computational comparison of the ESMs. These metrics are today used to compare HighResMIP simulations.
- the 4th workshop, held in Toulouse in 2016 and co-funded by IS-ENES2 and ESIWACE, brought the climate and weather communities together for the first time, both involved in the ESIWACE project. It was dedicated to high-resolution modelling and addressed the topic of the evolution of future computer architectures and how they should influence the development of next-generation of weather and climate models. An entire session was dedicated to the technological developments and new paradigms, in terms of languages and standards.

The 5th workshop has been organised by a Programme Committee (PC), whose members (in alphabetical order) have been identified by the HPC Task Force: Giovanni Aloisio (CMCC), Jean-Claude André

(affiliated to CERFACS), Peter Bauer (ECMWF), Joachim Biercamp (DKRZ), Reinhard Budich (MPI-M), Mick Carter (Met Office), Francisco Doblas-Reyes (BSC), Sandro Fiore (CMCC), Uwe Fladrich (SMHI), Sylvie Joussaume (IPSL), Bryan Lawrence (NCAS), Silvia Mocavero (CMCC), Antonio Navarra (CMCC), Kim Serradell (BSC), Sophie Valcke (CERFACS).

The PC selected the topics of the workshop and grouped them in the following 5 sessions:

- European & International Exascale Ecosystems – the session provided an overview of the main hardware and software initiatives at European and international level towards the exascale roadmap. Some European exascale projects, that already participated in the 4th workshop, were at a good stage or at the end and the main results have been presented
- Very high-resolution modelling and HPC challenges - the session provided an overview of the very high-resolution models towards 1-km simulations (already completed and ongoing developments), as well as the main challenges to make these simulations feasible and efficient on target hardware architectures
- Tools and components – the session provided an overview of tools, components and novel approaches (coupling, I/O, DSL, ...) meant to support the development of very high-resolution models
- Panel discussion on data centres support for weather and climate models and workflows – starting from the experience at the main European Climate and Weather data centres, an open discussion on community expectations, in terms of support, has been held
- Update on the European strategies on HPC – the session offered an overview of the European Technology Platform activities and research priorities

Some PC members have been designated as chairs of the scientific sessions and open discussions at the end of each day. The chairs were in charge of suggesting and inviting the speakers, preserving the right balance between European and international contributions. Finally, the PC defined the following workshop agenda (also available on the event webpage at the following link <https://www.esiwace.eu/events/5th-enes-hpc-workshop>):

Thursday 17 May 2018

08:30-09:00	<i>Registration & Welcome coffee</i>	
09:00-09:10	Welcome session	
09:00-09:05	Welcome	G. Aloisio (CMCC, IT)
09:05-09:10	Workshop introduction and opening remarks	J. Biercamp (DKRZ, DE)
09:10-11:50	Session 1 – European & international exascale ecosystems	Chairs: G. Aloisio/A. Navarra
09:10-09:40	Challenges of Exascale Computing, Redux	P. Messina (ANL, US)
09:40-10:10	The EuroHPC declaration	S. Bassini (CINECA, IT)
10:10-10:25	EXDCI – Supporting the European HPC ecosystem towards the Exascale endeavour	S. Bogaerts (PRACE, AISBL)
10:25-10:40	ESiWACE - Supporting very high-resolution climate simulations in Europe	J. Biercamp (DKRZ, DE)
10:40-11:05	<i>Coffee break</i>	
11:05-11:20	POP CoE: understanding applications and how to prepare for exascale	J. Labarta (BSC, SP)
11:20-11:35	The EoCoE Centre of Excellence	E. Audit (CEA, FR)
11:35-11:50	EuroEXA: a co-design project for exascale	G. Riley (Univ. of Manchester,

	computing	UK)
11:50-16:10	Session 2 – (Very) high-resolution models & HPC challenges	Chairs: J. Biercamp/R. Budich
11:50-12:10	Preliminary evaluation of systematic biases in a FV3-powered global cloud-permitting mode	S. J. Lin (NOAA, US)
12:10-12:30	Code optimizations and the accumulated impact on scientific throughput of an HPC centre	J. Dennis (NCAR, US)
12:30-13:30	<i>Networking lunch</i>	
13:30-13:50	Challenges of NICAM toward the exascale era	H. Yashiro (RIKEN, JP)
13:50-14:10	Redesigning CAM-SE on Sunway TaihuLight for Peta-Scale Performance	L. Gan (Tsinghua University, CN)
14:10-14:30	Near-global climate simulation at 1km resolution with COSMO 5.0	C. Osuna (MeteoSwiss, CH)
14:30-14:50	Tropical Cyclones and resolution sensitivity in HighResMIP GCMs	P. L. Vidale (NCAS, UK)
14:50-15:10	<i>Coffee break</i>	
15:10-15:30	The ESIWACE Demonstrators: Scalability, Performance Prediction, Evaluation	P. Neumann (DKRZ, DE)
15:30-15:50	DYNAMICO, the IPSL icosahedral dynamical core: status and outlook	T. Dubos (LMD/IPSL, FR)
15:50-16:10	Towards HPC System Throughput Optimization	J. Durachta (NOAA, US)
16:10-17:00	General discussion & end of day 1	Chair: P. Bauer
19:30	Workshop networking dinner	

Friday 18 May 2018

09:00-14:50	Session 3 – Tools & Components	Chairs: S. Valcke/K. Serradell
09:00-09:30	DSL toolchains and performance optimizations for weather and climate codes	C. Osuna (MeteoSwiss, CH)
09:30-10:00	Atlas, a library for numerical weather prediction and climate modelling	W. Deconinck (ECMWF, UK)
10:00-10:30	PSyclone: a domain-specific compiler for finite element/difference Earth-system modelling codes	R. Ford & A. Porter (STFC, UK)
10:30-10:50	<i>Coffee break</i>	
10:50-11:20	Efficiency and scalability of numerical algorithms - from ESCAPE to ESCAPE-2	P. Bauer (ECMWF, UK)
11:20-11:50	CLAW Compiler: Abstractions for Weather and Climate Models	V. Clément (MeteoSwiss, CH)
11:50-12:20	ESMF Strategies to Address HPC Challenges	R. Montuoro (NOAA/CIRES, US)
12:20-13:20	<i>Lunch break</i>	
13:20-13:50	Output whole CMIP6 data through the news XIOS parallel workflow functionalities	Y. Meurdesoif (IPSL, FR)
13:50-14:20	Latest developments on the OASIS3-MCT coupler for improved performance	S. Valcke (CERFACS, FR)
14:20-14:50	XIOS integration for OpenIFS: Computational	M. Acosta (BSC, SP)

Aspects and Performance Evaluation		
14:50-16:00	Session 4 - Panel Discussion (on data centre support for weather and climate models and workflows)	Chair: B. Lawrence
	Few minutes of presentation followed by questions and open discussion	CINECA, BSC, GENCI, JRC, CSCS, METO, ECMWF
16:00-16:20	<i>Coffee break</i>	
16:20-17:30	Session 5 – European strategies on HPC	Chairs: S. Jousaume/J.-C. André
16:20-17:00	An update on the ETP4HPC and Extreme Scale Demonstrators	T. Eickermann (Juelich & ETP4HPC)
17:00-17:30	Summary and further actions	Chair: J. Biercamp (DKRZ)
17:30	End of the workshop	

49 people attended the workshop. The audience was heterogeneous and included Climate and Weather scientists, HPC experts and vendors. About 55% of the attendees were speakers, internal and external to the ESIWACE project. About 49% of the attendees are involved in the project activities and about 80% of the participants are European.

Giovanni Aloisio, Silvia Mocavero and Antonio Aloisio have been in charge of the local organisation in Lecce. The workshop has been fully funded by ESIWACE.

Workshop outcomes

The workshop has focused on very high-resolution modelling. The community's current ambitious objective is to reach a global resolution of 1 km, which allows the explicit resolution of important processes (e.g. deep convection, gravity waves, ocean eddies) and the reduction of uncertainty in climate model projections, preserving a good performance level (at least 1SYPD) for the production model. Reaching this goal will be challenging and requires significant effort not only at a scientific level: the algorithms and the software stack have to be revised to fully exploit future hardware architectures. The workshop, like the previous ones, was a good opportunity to share the new developments at the different levels.

Some results about high-resolution multi-week global simulations with the ICON (double precision) and the IFS (single precision) have been shown, both at 5km on 900 Broadwell nodes (36 cores/node) with O(0.1-0.3) SYPD. Some tests with both models at 2.5km have also been performed in the context of the DYAMOND (DYNAMics of the Atmospheric general circulation Modeled On Non-hydrostatic Domains) project, which intercompares an emerging class of atmospheric circulation models. As a contribution to the DYAMOND project, several 40-day simulations have been done using the GFDL FV3 dycore. The experiments and preliminary analyses across the grey-zone at three different horizontal resolutions (13, 6.5, and 3.25km) have been presented, showing that 6.5km has the smallest bias in 500-mb HGHT over the 40-day period. 6 hours with ~55K cores Cray XC40 are needed to complete a 40-day sub-seasonal prediction. The NICAM model, which plays a key role in Japan also for the configuration of the post-K supercomputer as one of the proxy applications for its evaluation, contributes to the DYAMOND project with the experiments at 14, 7, 3.5km. Recent performance optimisations allowed the achievement of a good strong scalability of the model at 14km on the K computer with a SYPD of 0.64 on 20,480 cores. The big data analysis issue due to the post-processing of the huge amount of data produced by the first NICAM global sub-km weather simulation, has been addressed through the analysis on icosahedral grid directly performed on the K computer. Finally, some near-global simulations at a fixed horizontal resolution performed with the COSMO regional model have been presented: simulations at 1.9km are

executed on 4,888 hybrid nodes (Intel Haswell + NVIDIA Tesla P100) of the Piz Daint supercomputer with a SYPD of 0.23.

At the hardware level, the presented EuroHPC initiative is the joint effort of some European States to provide a common HPC and Data infrastructure for a wide range of fields, with a mid-term and long-term hardware roadmap (two pre-exascale systems by 2021, two exascale systems by 2023). At the same time, the HPC research landscape includes a list of projects (started in 2015 and close to the end), some of which are focussed on the Climate & Weather field while others refer to cross-cutting activities. The workshop allowed a better understanding of their impact in terms of (i) support to the whole HPC ecosystem towards exascale (e.g. EXDCI), (ii) numerical algorithms evolution to improve their efficiency and scalability on novel processors (e.g. ESCAPE), (iii) development of tools to understand the applications behaviour and to prepare them for exascale through new programming best practices (e.g. POP), (iv) definition of a new software stack that takes into account the hardware infrastructure following a co-design approach (e.g. EuroEXA).

Great emphasis has been placed on the development and integration of tools, which help to address the main computational issues due to the very high-resolution, such as the I/O overhead that increases both with the resolution and the number of parallel tasks. The XIOS tool, for example, allows optimising I/O and post-processing operations and overlapping them with the computation. During the workshop, the main new developments of the tool were shown as well as the advantages of its integration within complex systems such as EC-Earth, one of the ESMs recently used to run some high-resolution experiments under PRIMAVERA, an H2020 project about the design and execution of a HighResMIP exercise, using six GCMs with a target resolution of ~20km.

A complementary aspect of the high-resolution is the Earth System Model complexity, which requires the integration of efficient coupling systems (e.g. the OASIS-MCT coupler), able to scale on thousands of cores when the spatial domain size increases. Moreover, the workshop promoted the discussion about the use of new methodologies for model development based on DSL (Domain Specific Languages). The main goal is the improvement of the performance portability, taking into account the rapid change of the hardware architectures and the adoption of heterogeneous systems. The technology trend actually asks for a great effort to optimise the codes on different architectures, while also taking into account the issues related to code maintenance. Code implementation and maintenance costs can be reduced by removing implementation details from the model (abstraction). Even if the approach is already under evaluation by the community, it has been shown that some tools (e.g. PSyclone and GridTools), based on the separation of concerns concept, allow reducing the time and cost of performance portability. The results of their application in some case studies (e.g. LFRic and COSMO) were shared during the workshop. The use of GridTools demonstrated the portability of the generated code (the same numerical code compiles and runs on multiple architecture backends) and the performance speedup w.r.t. the code baseline (due to library optimisations). However, the right level of abstraction needed for porting the code to DSL, requires changing the current model development practices (porting to DSL is still a considerable effort) and expertise. The integration of the PSyclone tool into the LFRic system allowed developing hybrid MPI+OpenMP code without changing the scientific code, even if the use of the tool is restricted to HPC experts.

Finally, the workshop has been enriched with an open discussion about the role of data centres in supporting climate & weather research activities. The community doesn't only need access to the systems, but also a suitable software stack to efficiently run the models on novel architectures as well as tools to access and deliver the large amount of data produced by the simulations.

Some general remarks can be made. The workshop, like the previous ones, was an opportunity to exchange information among different communities. Weather and Climate communities are increasingly closer in terms of requirements and designed solutions, due to the common efforts within the ESIWACE project. The need to interconnect hardware and software developments remains a key factor. The

participation of some vendors in the workshop and their involvement in the ESIWACE project are of great relevance, even if the roadmap towards a bilateral co-design is still long.

Since the need for very high-resolution simulation capabilities imposes many computing and science challenges on model developers, the main contribution of this workshop was to provide an open window on the progresses already made and to identify and discuss some open questions:

How much domain specific developments are really needed?

The usefulness of general purpose computing for the community needs appears to be limited, certainly when we look ahead at very high-resolution simulation capabilities for producing a step-change in predictive skill. This applies to both weather and climate simulations in the same way. In fact, the ExtremeEarth proposal claims that we need a substantial investment in both hardware and software developments to make this happen, and we also say that incremental advances will plateau and never provide what's needed.

So the proposal is to invest in domain specific technology, again for both software and hardware. And this would be a true interpretation of co-design. How much domain specific hardware can be and needs to be designed is an open question. It might well be that processor technology will be fine, and the domain specific aspect is really about assembly, e.g. very fast inter-connects over HPC sub-domains (a la fat nodes), a dense hierarchy of memory to do post-processing on the fly etc.

For software we realise that existing programming models cause problems for both portability and performance. Ideally, we follow the principle of the separation of concerns whereby we separate between high-level science code levels at the top and highly optimized, hardware specific kernel libraries at the bottom. What sits in between needs to be defined and could be automated code translation or domain-specific code layers. To truly develop a generic software framework for our community is a real challenge. Projects like ESCAPE, ESCAPE-2 and ESIWACE-2 (but also EuroEXA) invest in this, but this is clearly not enough. This means, that our community has to make important strategic decisions about how to realise domain specificity in an economic and effective way. These decisions may not be in line with European hardware development programmes like EuroHPC.

When will we be able to synchronise advanced developments with operational production of predictions?

Operations in both weather and climate need to run reliably on robust technology 24/7. This implies that progress is incremental and the uptake of new technologies needs to undergo serious scrutiny. This is why procurements in Climate and Weather field are rather conservative, and this has worked fairly well in the past. As our requirements grow faster than Moore's law and code efficiency (sustained/peak performance is declining), we will reach the limits of affordability very soon though.

At the same time we are investing in novel methods exploring new technologies, but we realize that in many cases substantial parts of our codes need to be entirely reconfigured (see also 1st discussion point). Even mathematical approaches and algorithms, that we assumed to be stable due to their scientific performance, need to be reassessed because they may not perform computationally well enough in the future. We may have to sacrifice accuracy for speed.

While projects like ESIWACE take care of the incremental side of things (e.g. how to adapt existing codes to near-future machines like EuroHPC enabling future CMIPs to be feasible), projects like ESCAPE-1&2, NextGenIO, EuroEXA etc. trial much more advanced options. How we bring those together without delaying operational performance but, at the same time, migrating new methodologies into operations is currently unclear. There is a gap between incremental and radically new technologies that we don't know how to bridge.

Do we really pay enough attention to the convergence between compute and data?

Data handling bottlenecks are at the core of many computing bottlenecks. Having data awareness while analysing and solving compute issues is key.

When it comes to data archiving and dissemination, we do not even know how to deal with say 1 km model output, even if we could compute it fast enough. Do we have to degrade model output for efficient data handling at the expense of the actual information we were after in the first place? How to we reduce volume without sacrificing information?

These questions will define the ongoing discussions in our community with high relevance for the adaptation of weather and climate prediction codes to future HPC infrastructures with a particular focus on EuroHPC. These issues will continue to be addressed during the next workshops planned for 2020 (in Hamburg) and 2022 (in Barcelona).

5. References (*Bibliography*)

None

6. Dissemination and uptake

6.1 Dissemination

Slides and abstracts of the talks have been provided by the speakers, collected by the organisation team and made available on the ESIWACE website, at the following link: <https://www.esiwace.eu/events/5th-enes-hpc-workshop/presentations/>

6.2 Uptake by the targeted audience

As indicated in the Description of the Action, the audience for this deliverable is: the General Public (PU).

This is how we are going to ensure the uptake of the deliverables by the targeted audience

- All the material is in full open access here: <https://www.esiwace.eu/events/5th-enes-hpc-workshop/presentations/>
- The materials will be circulated to wider communities via the ESIWACE newsletter
- The outputs of the workshop will be also widely promoted at the dissemination events planned by ESIWACE community in 2018.

7. The delivery is delayed: Yes No

The delivery of this report is not delayed.

8. Changes made and/or difficulties encountered, if any

The workshop was initially planned for March 2018 (DoA) but it had to be delayed to May 2018 because was not possible to find an earlier date for the workshop due to existing commitments of the speakers invited to the event.

9. Sustainability

9.1. Lessons learnt: both positive and negative that can be drawn from the experiences of the work to date

The workshop pointed out the role of the European scientific and HPC communities in the international context, showing the progress in the development of both models and HPC technologies. These exchange opportunities help us take stock of the situation and establish the priorities for the future, as well as sharing the results of the work done in order to efficiently program the short and medium-term research activities.

9.2 Links built with other deliverables, WPs, and synergies created with other projects

The workshop strengthened the synergy with other European projects, pointing out the role of the ESIWACE project within the European HPC ecosystem. The potential links among the different initiatives have been discussed and new collaborations could start. A strong intra-project link with WP2 activities should be mentioned due to the strict relationship between the workshop main theme (very high-resolution & HPC solutions) and the main focus of WP2, namely high-resolution demonstrator development and related scalability issues.

10. Dissemination activities

Type of dissemination and communication activities	Number	Total funding amount	Type of audience reached In the context of all dissemination & communication activities ('multiple choices' is possible)	Estimated number of persons reached
Organisation of a workshop	1	See form C of the organising partners	Scientific Community (higher education, Research, Industry)	50

Intellectual property rights resulting from this deliverable

Not applicable